

Some Solutions to Improve the Quality of Work to Get Feedback from Learners about Teaching Activities of Lecturers

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Abstract:

This report aims to provide some solutions to improve the quality of the work of getting feedback from learners about teaching activities of lecturers at the Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology. Through this activity to assess the status of the teaching quality of the teaching staff. Thereby, building teachers with ethical qualities, professional conscience, improving pedagogical capacity and quality of lectures, and through this activity also helps the school to raise the sense of responsibility. in implementing training objectives, currently. On the students' side, it also contributes to improving the sense of responsibility in implementing regulations on training and awareness raising in learning and research; create conditions for learners to reflect their thoughts and aspirations to express their opinions about the quality of lecturers' lectures

Keywords: Solutions, quality, feedback.

1. Introduction

The world is entering the new millennium with the explosion of information, the rapid development of high technology, the knowledge economy and the trend of globalization. The Party and the State advocated to promote industrialization and modernization, implement the strategy of rich people, strong countries, fair, democratic and civilized society. In this context, higher education, has a major role in training and development. With the viewpoint of "investment in education is investment in development", our country has more and more guidelines, policies as well as solutions to focus on improving the quality of higher education. In which, the evaluation of the teaching quality of lecturers of higher education institutions is one of the concerns of the education - training and social sectors. There are many forms of evaluation of teaching activities of teachers / lecturers such as: Self-evaluation of teachers, evaluation through opinions of colleagues, leaders, through teaching records, learning outcomes of students students - students etc ... and through the opinions of students - students. The results of teacher evaluation can help them know whether their teaching is effective, thereby knowing the defect in teaching and strengthening knowledge, constantly improving knowledge, innovating the way teaching methods, quality assurance for the teaching process. At the same time, creating a close relationship between teachers and students but not losing the tradition of "religious teacher".

From the academic year 2009 - 2010 up to now, Dien Bien College of Economics - Engineering conducted feedback on the teaching activities of lecturers through learners, this is a new activity with many impacts. positive to the teaching activities of the lecturers, however, there are still some limitations on the form, method and method of data processing.

We hope this scientific research will contribute to improving the quality of activities to get feedback at the Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology in particular and the training institutions in general, on that basis. High quality teaching activities.

2. Content

2.1. Actual status of collecting feedback at school

Students assessing the teaching activities of teachers are no longer a new issue for our higher education, most universities and colleges have applied and brought certain effects for digging. create.

Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology with the function of training and fostering human resources at the college level and lower level to serve the socio-economic development of Dien Bien province and neighboring provinces. close. In order to achieve the goal of training good quality human resources, meeting the increasing demands of society, the school regularly pays attention to improving the quality of teachers / lecturers, thereby improving the quality. educate. One of the measures to improve the quality of teaching staff is the evaluation of teachers / lecturers through learner surveys. From the academic year 2009 - 2010 up to now, Dien Bien College of Economics - Engineering has taken feedback from the learners about the teaching activities of lecturers. It can be seen that the school has been very interested in this activity and implemented quite well in the past, however, because this activity still has some certain limitations, one of the limitations of this activity was:

- The form and content of the votes are not really scientific:
- + The questionnaire of the question is qualitative and difficult to quantify when processing research results.
- + Survey questionnaire is not comprehensive, just stop at getting feedback from learners about the quality of lecturers' lectures, though it is a decisive stage in all stages of training.
- How to conduct comments is not effective:
- + Time to organize the votes is not appropriate, usually issued in the time of class preparation. Therefore, learners will lack the focus, the loudspeaker, roughly.
- + Voters have not yet instructed and disseminated the meaning of getting feedback, so some students have the idea that collecting opinions is only a form, or avoid it, so they only finish their work and do not guarantee ensure objectivity.
- How to handle data is still manual, time-consuming: Questionnaires are closed questions, so when processing data, it is difficult to apply support software but perform manual statistics, accuracy level Not high, take a long time.

2.2. Solution

* Design feedback form

Design survey sheets to get learners' comments about teaching activities of lecturers with the following major contents:

- 1) The implementation of teaching regulations and pedagogical style;
- 2) Teaching content;
- 3) Methods, means and organization of teaching;
- 4) Check and evaluate;

The content and form of the votes are agreed through a conference to solicit opinions of the leaders of the school and the management units. The survey questionnaire was designed with 19 closed questions with the content covered above (see Appendix 1) in addition to 5 open questions for students to assess more about teachers / lecturers and about subjects. The questionnaire uses a scale of 4 levels (Level 1: Weak; Level 2: = Average; Level 3: = Pretty; Level 4: = Good).

N ₀	CONSULTATION CONTENT	Degree evaluation			
		T (4)	K (3)	Tb(2)	Y (1)
I. The implementation of teaching regulations and pedagogical style					
1	Be sure to go to class on time and have enough time to teach				
2	Implementing the teaching according to the timetable, informing students in advance when changing the teaching schedule				
3	Do not use mobile phones, do personal work affecting lectures and students				
4	Dress neatly, polite manners (according to the Regulations of the school office)				
II. teaching content					
5	At the beginning of the module, teachers / lecturers introduce syllabus, objectives, learning materials, references, testing methods - evaluation				
6	Academic knowledge is regularly updated, with examples attached to practice				
7	Having a strong knowledge helps students to understand the focus and answer the questions satisfactorily				
8	Keep abreast of the objectives and content of the course according to the schedule like the outline and schedule				
9	The content of the lesson is accurate, clear and vivid				
III. Methods, means and teaching organization					
10	The ability to express and communicate pedagogy				
11	Enthusiastic, responsible in teaching and managing classes; respect, care, help students				
12	Teaching methods create excitement, attracting the attention of students				
13	Flexible teaching methods, suitable to each content of the module; promote positive, creative thinking, self-study, self-study of students				
14	Encourage students to ask questions, discuss, take initiative and actively participate in lessons				
15	Helping HSSV students understand key knowledge				
16	To effectively use teaching aids: projectors, pictures, tapes, computers, radios ... suitable to the specific characteristics of the module				
IV. Check					
17	Exams and tests are suitable for content, synthesizing many parts of the module and encouraging creativity				
18	Fair, objective, accurate				
19	Mark and return items in a timely manner, with comments and useful reviews for students				

* Innovate how to get feedback

Based on the practical implementation of feedback feedback currently being implemented at the school, we adjust the way to get feedback by following 4 steps:

Step 1: Deploy the Plan and the list of lecturers will get feedback, a sample of lecturer evaluation forms and documents to guide the Faculties;

Step 2: Conduct feedback for teachers. Time to get feedback on the last session of the module. Officers are tasked with distributing feedback forms to provide technical guidance, explaining the meaning, rights and responsibilities for students when participating in the assessment.

Step 3: Processing the data obtained from the evaluation forms, analyzing technical conclusions, making recommendations to improve the quality of teaching.

Step 4: Inform the survey data and conclusions by E-mail to teachers / lecturers to adjust the teaching activities accordingly; send a general report to the Faculty manager and the school's leaders for consideration. For lecturers whose assessment results are not high, especially lecturers who have many negative feedbacks from students - students will be met directly by the school leaders to discuss and take measures to foster overcome limitations.

* Innovate how to handle collected data

Processing results obtained by SPSS software 18.0:

* Design the table and enter the data obtained.

* Processing data and writing reports for each lecturer, each department and synthesizing the whole school.

3. Conclusion

Thus, collecting feedback from learners is a useful and necessary information source for improving training quality. Therefore, it is necessary to synchronize the above solutions to bring the highest efficiency. In the process of assessing the teaching activities of teachers, students need to take seriously, accurately and objectively, ensuring that lecturer feedback accurately reflects the teaching activities conducted, Since then, lecturers have more information to adjust teaching activities to meet learners' needs, improve the quality of training and teaching quality. - In addition to the comments for the available criteria, students need to have additional comments through open questions, the students' comments will be useful information to help Teachers' teaching is conducted better.

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APPENDIX

COMMENTS FOR CONSULTING PEOPLE

ABOUT TEACHING ACTIVITIES OF TEACHERS / TEACHERS

In the spirit of respecting learners' opinions, the school takes opinions of students (students, students) about teaching activities of teachers / lecturers. Their straightforward, objective and honest opinions are an important information channel for teachers / lecturers to adjust their teaching activities, contributing to further improving the quality of teaching. The school thanks and welcomes your comments.

Full name of teacher / lecturer:

Term: **Class**

Semester: **201 academic year ... - 201**

I give my opinion by checking (X) to the appropriate levels.

No	CONSULTATION CONTENT	DEGREE EVALUATION			
		T	K	TB	Y
I. The implementation of teaching regulations and pedagogical style					
1	Be sure to go to class on time and have enough time to teach				
2	Implementing the teaching according to the timetable, informing students in advance when changing the teaching schedule				
3	Do not use mobile phones, do personal work affecting lectures and students				
4	Dress neatly, polite manners (according to the Regulations of the school office)				
II. teaching content					
5	At the beginning of the module, teachers / lecturers introduce the outline, objectives, learning materials, references, testing methods - evaluation				
6	Academic knowledge is regularly updated, with examples attached to practice				
7	Having a strong knowledge helps students to understand the focus and answer the questions satisfactorily				
8	Keep abreast of the objectives and content of the course according to the schedule like the outline and schedule				
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13	Flexible teaching methods, suitable to each content of the module; promote positive, creative thinking, self-study, self-study of students				
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15	Helping HSSV students understand key knowledge				
16	To effectively use teaching aids: projectors, pictures, tapes, computers, radios ... suitable to the specific characteristics of the module				
IV. Check					
17	Exams and tests are suitable for content, synthesizing many parts of the module and encouraging creativity				
18	Fair, objective, accurate				
19	Mark and return items in a timely manner, with comments and useful reviews for students				

V. Please give me the following information:

1. The ratio of your class time to this module:

100% 80% - less than 100% Less than 80%

2. My general feeling about the quality of this module teaching:

3. Please indicate the points to be adjusted in this module's teaching activity:

4. In your opinion, what should the school do to improve the quality of this module:

5. Other comments: